

THE CURRENT RELEVANCE OF DILATIONAL CARDIOMYOPATHY.

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Relevance of the topic. Dilated cardiomyopathy (DCM) is a pathological condition of the heart muscle tissue, in which the systolic function of the heart decreases, manifested by dilation of the left ventricle. In this disease, a decrease in myocardial contractility reduces the cardiac output (circulatory efficiency), which leads to systolic dysfunction and decompensation of pulmonary and systemic circulation. The number of people suffering from this disease is increasing in countries around the world, including in our republic, regardless of political and economic conditions. In recent years, cardiologists have become increasingly interested in non-coronary myocardial diseases among cardiovascular diseases, due to the increasing number of patients with dilated cardiomyopathy (DCMP), which causes premature disability and death of able-bodied people.

The purpose of the scientific work. The purpose of the work is to study the complications arising from repeated administration of general anesthetics in surgical practice at the Khorezm branch of the Russian State Institute of Surgical Oncology.

Materials and methods. The medical histories of patients who applied to the Khorezm branch of the Russian State Institute of Internal Medicine for various types of surgical procedures in 2022-2023 were retrospectively studied.

The results obtained. During the studies, it was found that out of 100 patients who underwent surgery, 20 had arrhythmia, 25 had angina. In 40 patients, when repeated general anesthesia was performed, slight changes in arterial blood pressure of patients during surgery were detected. Pathological conditions were not detected in the remaining patients.

In conclusion, it can be said that it is recommended to conduct clinical and laboratory examinations of any patients before undergoing surgical procedures.

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